

Research article

Mathematical modeling of tumor nanomechanical fingerprints: A weighted skew-normal distribution approach for cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring

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ABSTRACT

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is a key method for nanomechanical characterization of cells and tissues, with AFM-derived fingerprints proposed as biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring. These signatures typically include a higher elasticity peak (HEP), reflecting extracellular matrix stiffening due to collagen overproduction, and a lower elasticity peak (LEP), indicative of cancer cell softening. Despite their potential, AFM elasticity spectra are often assessed qualitatively, and a standardized mathematical framework for quantitative analysis is lacking. Here, we provide a rigorous mathematical characterization of Young's modulus distribution in normal and cancerous tissues, aiming to improve cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring. Previously published AFM elasticity spectra from murine tumors were employed and analyzed to evaluate tumor nanomechanical changes at different time points, 14, 21, and 28 days after cell implantation, including both untreated controls and a tranilast-treated group, with tranilast being a drug known to reduce collagen levels. The weighted skew-normal distribution was employed to model AFM data due to its ability to capture the two-peak structure of cancerous tissue, reflecting a mixture of soft cancer cells and stiffer components. We hypothesized that tranilast treatment would progressively shift the HEP to lower values. Model accuracy was confirmed by high R^2 values and low Cramér–von Mises (CvM) criteria. Results revealed a transition from a two-peak distribution in controls (HEP and LEP) to peak convergence in tranilast-treated tissue at 28 days. We conclude that the weighted skew-normal distribution offers a robust method for quantifying tumor nanomechanics, which is related to therapeutic outcomes.

1. Introduction

Cancer progression has been linked to modifications in the mechanical behavior of tumor cells, arising from structural and mechanical alterations within the tumor microenvironment (TME) [1–3]. As tumors expand within the surrounding healthy tissue, they often become stiffer, a phenomenon that is more evident in certain subtypes of breast and pancreatic cancers as well as in sarcomas. This increase in stiffness mainly results from the accumulation of structural components of the tumor extracellular matrix (ECM), such as collagen, along with elevated numbers of stromal cells, giving rise to desmoplasia, a cancer-specific

form of fibrosis. Tumor stiffening may lead to compression of intratumoral blood vessels that impairs their function, creating significant pathophysiological obstacles to efficient drug delivery and thus, reducing treatment effectiveness [4,5]. Moreover, it is well established that restoring the mechanical properties of a tumor, either by targeting components of the ECM or by reprogramming cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), enhances blood vessel function, thereby improving the delivery of anticancer agents and ultimately boosting therapeutic efficacy [6–10]. Tumor mechanical properties can be normalized through mechanotherapeutics, which involve repurposing approved drugs with anti-fibrotic or CAF-reprogramming effects [11], such as the

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Fig. 1. (a) Plot of the p.d.f. of a normal distribution for different values of σ ($\mu = 10$). (b) Plot of the p.d.f. of a skew-normal distribution for different values of ξ ($\omega = 0, \alpha = 1$). (c) Plot of the p.d.f. of a skew-normal distribution for different values of ω ($\xi = 0, \alpha = 1$). (d) Plot of the p.d.f. of a skew-normal distribution for different values of α ($\xi = 0, \omega = 1$).

antihistamine tranilast [12–14], the anti-fibrotic agent pirfenidone [15], the corticosteroid dexamethasone [16], and the antihypertensives losartan and bosentan [8,17–20].

There is now a pressing need for the development of biomarkers that can assess the mechanical state of tumors, facilitating personalized treatment strategies and enabling the monitoring of mechanotherapeutic approaches designed to modify the tumor’s mechanical micro-environment and improve therapy [5,6]. Biomarkers play a crucial role in cancer diagnosis and prognosis [21] by enabling early detection, monitoring disease progression, and guiding therapeutic decisions. Recent work has shown that mechanical alterations are not limited to tissues but extend down to the level of chromosomes [22]. Chromosome mechanics are critical for genomic stability, and changes in their elasticity have been linked to mitotic errors, cancer progression, and epigenetic modifications. In this context, atomic force microscopy (AFM) [23] has been employed to evaluate the mechanical properties of cancer tissue and AFM-based mechanical characterization of tumor biopsies has been shown to hold potential for cancer diagnosis [3,24–27]. AFM studies have demonstrated that treatments such as valproic acid can modify chromosome elasticity and stretching modulus, reflecting underlying chromatin reorganization [22]. These findings highlight the broader significance of mechanical signatures in disease and strengthen the motivation for developing robust mathematical descriptions of modulus distributions, as pursued in this study. AFM allows researchers to capture key biomechanical features of tumors, such as tumor stiffening. Studies in human breast biopsies have revealed distinct nanomechanical signatures, with stiffness quantified in terms of Young’s modulus. Normal and benign tissues exhibit one-peak Young’s modulus distributions, whereas malignant tissues display two separate peaks [26]. Similar bimodal Young’s modulus distributions, referred to as the

lower elasticity peak (LEP) and higher elasticity peak (HEP), have also been observed in human liver tissue and various other cancers, including esophageal, renal, colon, and papillary carcinomas [3,27]. AFM has further been applied to classify brain tumors based on their nanomechanical properties [28], and clustering algorithms have been developed to categorize stiffness measurements into cellular, noncellular, and fibrous tissue components, enabling the identification of multiple tissue types [29]. Research on cervical cancer demonstrated bimodal distributions of Young’s modulus, with increased HEP values in malignant samples, suggesting that HEP may serve as a nanomechanical biomarker [30]. Comparable stiffness patterns have also been observed in pancreatic cancer and sarcoma, with AFM aiding in the monitoring of cancer progression and treatment response [31–33]. Interestingly, similar patterns in AFM elasticity spectra have been reported in other pathological conditions, such as pulmonary fibrosis, highlighting the potential of AFM-based biomarkers beyond cancer [34]. It is also interesting to note that neural networks have been applied for the automated detection of nanomechanical signatures in brain cancer [35]. Collectively, these findings highlight AFM as a powerful tool for early cancer diagnosis, tumor grading, monitoring disease progression, and evaluating therapeutic outcomes [35–38]. The single-peak and two-peak distributions of Young’s modulus are described using the weighted skew-normal distribution. Subsequently, data from murine breast cancer tissues treated with the anti-fibrotic drug tranilast are modeled to evaluate the drug’s effects, tracking the transformation from a two-peak to a single-peak profile and quantitatively assessing treatment impact. Our findings highlight that the weighted skew-normal distribution effectively models Young’s modulus distributions in cancerous tissues, captures peak convergence under tranilast treatment, and emphasizes its broader applicability to heterogeneous and

Fig. 2. Plot of the p.d.f. of a weighted skew-normal distribution (far right) for different values of w .

multi-peak stiffness profiles in cancer and fibrotic diseases.

2. Data set and mathematical model

2.1. Data set

We used a dataset of AFM-based elasticity spectra published in [33]. The dataset includes spectra obtained from biopsies of murine breast tumors from two groups: (i) saline-treated controls and (ii) tranilast-treated. A detailed description of the experimental procedures is provided in the original publication [33]. Briefly, orthotopic breast tumors were generated by implantation of 5×10^4 E0771 cells into the third mammary fat pad of 6–8-week-old C57BL/6 mice. Tranilast treatment (200 mg/kg, orally) was initiated once the average breast tumor volume reached 200 mm³ (on day 14 after cancer cell implantation) and was administered daily for 14 days. Biopsies were collected at 14, 21, and 28 days post-implantation using a semi-automatic biopsy instrument (18 G, COOK). AFM measurements were performed within 1–72 h following tumor removal. Elasticity spectra were acquired with a commercial AFM system (Molecular Imaging-Agilent PicoPlus AFM) using silicon nitride cantilevers (MLCT-Bio, cantilever D, Bruker Company). The maximum applied loading force was set to 1.8 nN and Young's modulus values were calculated based on the Hertz-Sneddon contact mechanics framework, assuming a Poisson's ratio of 0.5 [39–41]. AFM measurements were obtained from 6 to 7 force maps ($20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, 16×16 grids) per specimen, yielding 256 force–displacement curves per map and approximately 1500 curves per mouse. Four mice were analyzed in total: two in the first experiment (Dataset 1) and two in the second experiment (Dataset 2), each including one control and one Tranilast-treated animal.

2.2. Mathematical model

2.2.1. Definitions

Let \mathcal{X} be a continuous random variable (c.r.v.). The integrable function $f_{\mathcal{X}} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called the probability density function (p.d.f.) of the c.r.v. \mathcal{X} , if [42,43]:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_{\mathcal{X}}(x) dx = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\int_a^b f_{\mathcal{X}}(x) dx = \Pr(a \leq \mathcal{X} \leq b) \quad (2)$$

where $\Pr(a < \mathcal{X} \leq b)$ denotes the probability the c.r.v. \mathcal{X} lies within the interval $[a, b]$. The notation $\mathcal{X} \sim f(x)$ is commonly used to specify that the p.d.f. of \mathcal{X} is the function $f_{\mathcal{X}}(x)$. The function:

$$F_{\mathcal{X}}(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f_{\mathcal{X}}(t) dt = \Pr(\mathcal{X} \leq x) \quad (3)$$

is called the cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.) of the c.r.v. \mathcal{X} [42–44].

2.2.2. The normal distribution

The c.r.v. \mathcal{X} is called normal, with parameters $\mu \in \mathbb{R}, \sigma > 0$, and we write $\mathcal{X} \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, when its p.d.f. is given by [42–44]:

$$f_{\mathcal{X}}(x; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4)$$

It is well known that the plot of $f_{\mathcal{X}}$ is a symmetric curve around $x = \mu$ and a measure of its spread is given by σ (Fig. 1a). It can be shown that μ equals to the mean value of \mathcal{X} whereas σ^2 equals to the variance of \mathcal{X} [42,43].

2.2.3. The standard normal distribution

It can be shown [42,43] that if $\mathcal{X} \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ the c.r.v. $\mathcal{Z} \equiv (\mathcal{X} - \mu) / \sigma \sim N(0, 1)$, that is:

$$\varphi(x) \equiv f_{\mathcal{Z}}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (5)$$

and \mathcal{Z} is called a standard normal r.v. Its c.d.f. is given by [44]:

$$\Phi(x) \equiv F_{\mathcal{Z}}(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x \varphi(t) dt, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (6)$$

2.2.4. The skew-normal distribution

Following [45], let \mathcal{Y} be a c.r.v. with p.d.f.:

$$f_{\mathcal{Y}}(x; a) = 2\varphi(x)\Phi(ax), \quad x, a \in \mathbb{R} \quad (7)$$

It can be readily seen that for $a = 0$, \mathcal{Y} becomes a standard normal r.v. since $f_{\mathcal{Y}}(x; 0) = 2\varphi(x)\Phi(0) = \varphi(x)$, owing to $\Phi(0) = 1/2$.

Now let:

$$\mathcal{Y} \equiv \xi + \omega \mathcal{V}, \quad \xi \in \mathbb{R}, \omega \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (8)$$

It can be shown that the p.d.f. of the c.r.v. \mathcal{Y} is given by [45]:

$$f_{\mathcal{Y}}(x; \xi, \omega^2, a) = \frac{2}{\omega} \varphi\left(\frac{x-\xi}{\omega}\right) \Phi\left(a \frac{x-\xi}{\omega}\right), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (9)$$

and the r.v. is called a skew-normal r.v. with location parameter ξ , scale parameter ω , and shape (or slant) parameter a ; symbolically $\mathcal{Y} \sim \text{SN}(\xi, \omega^2, a)$. It is readily seen that for $\xi = 0, \omega = 1$ and $a = 0$, $\mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{V} \sim f_{\mathcal{V}}(x; 0) = N(0, 1)$; thus, the standard normal distribution is a special case of a skew-normal distribution.

The parameter ξ determines the location of the maximum of the distribution (c.f. with the role of μ in $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ distribution) (Fig. 1b). The parameter $\omega > 0$ determines the spread of the distribution (c.f. with the role of σ in $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ distribution) (Fig. 1c). Finally, the parameter a controls the direction and the magnitude of the skewness of the distribution. In fact, when $a > 0$ the SN distribution is right-skewed, whereas for $a < 0$ is left-skewed [45,46], as can also be verified by Fig. 1d.

2.2.5. The weighted skew-normal distribution

We say that the c.r.v. \mathcal{B} follows a *weighted skew-normal* distribution with parameter $\mathbf{p} \equiv (\xi_1, \omega_1^2, a_1, \xi_2, \omega_2^2, a_2)$, when its p.d.f. is given by:

$$f_{\mathcal{B}}(x; \mathbf{p}) = w f_{\text{SN}}(x; \xi_1, \omega_1^2, a_1) + (1-w) f_{\text{SN}}(x; \xi_2, \omega_2^2, a_2), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (10)$$

where $0 \leq w \leq 1$ is a *weight coefficient* [47]. Clearly, for $w = 1$, $\mathcal{B} \sim \text{SN}(\xi_1, \omega_1^2, a_1)$, whereas for $w = 0$, $\mathcal{B} \sim \text{SN}(\xi_2, \omega_2^2, a_2)$. For any value $0 < w < 1$ a mixture of two skew-normal distributions is received. It is apparent that as $w \rightarrow 1^-$, $f_{\mathcal{B}}$ is dominated by the features of the $\text{SN}(\xi_1, \omega_1^2, a_1)$, whereas as $w \rightarrow 0^+$ by those of the $\text{SN}(\xi_2, \omega_2^2, a_2)$. For any intermediate value of w , $f_{\mathcal{B}}$ possesses mixed features of the two skew-normal distributions invoked in (10) (Fig. 2).

It should be stressed that a weighted skew-normal distribution is generally a bimodal distribution (i.e., it has two peaks); this property is of paramount importance for the analysis of the data presented below.

2.2.6. Statistical measures of fitting accuracy

The Young's modulus spectra of the experimental data used in this paper were represented as histograms of probability densities, constructed using 10 bins in each case. Each bin corresponds to a range of modulus values, and the number of data points within that range determines the bin height. Ten bins were selected to balance resolution and clarity, providing sufficient detail to capture single- or double-peak patterns in stiffness while avoiding over-fragmentation of the data and preserving statistical robustness.

To quantitatively assess the agreement between the fitted curve and the experimentally obtained data, the classical R-squared coefficient and

14 days: Dataset 1

Fig. 3. Experimental data and fitted curves from a representative dataset (Dataset 1), corresponding to 14 days after cancer cell implantation. **(a)** Control sample and **(b)** tranilast-treated sample. **(c)** Comparison of the two fitted curves. For the control group, two distinct peaks are observed ($\xi_1 = 0.9393kPa$, $\xi_2 = 1.8491kPa$) whereas tranilast treatment produces a single-peak distribution ($\xi_1 = 0.8250kPa$), indicating a clear effect of the treatment. In both cases, the R^2 coefficient and CvM metric were close to 1 and 0, respectively, demonstrating high fitting accuracy. **(d)** The cumulative probability functions are shown in for the control and the **(e)** tranilast-treated samples, respectively, further illustrating the quality of the fit.

the Cramér-von Mises (CvM) criterion were applied. The CvM metric is particularly suitable for capturing differences in the overall shape of cumulative distribution functions (CDFs), making it appropriate for distinguishing between normal and malignant tissue distributions. Specifically, the CvM criterion measures the integrated squared difference between the empirical CDF of the data and the CDF predicted by the theoretical model. In particular, let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{10}\}$ denote the normalized relative frequencies of the empirical histogram over n bins. In addition, $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_{10}\}$ represent the corresponding normalized values obtained from the fitted probability density function (Eq. 10) evaluated and integrated over the same bins. The empirical cumulative distribution function is defined as:

$$CDF_{P(j)} = \sum_{i=1}^j P_i, \quad j = 1, \dots, 10 \quad (11)$$

In addition, the fitted cumulative distribution function:

$$CDF_{Q(j)} = \sum_{i=1}^j Q_i, \quad j = 1, \dots, 10 \quad (12)$$

The CvM metric is defined as follows:

$$CvM = \sum_{j=1}^{10} (CDF_{P(j)} - CDF_{Q(j)})^2 \quad (13)$$

The above sum (Eq. 13) represents the integrated squared deviation between the cumulative distributions. A small CvM value (i.e., close to zero) indicates strong agreement between the shapes of the empirical histogram and the fitted distribution. It is important to note that discrepancies between the empirical and fitted distributions may partly originate from low-probability bins (i.e., “small bins”), which are often underrepresented or neglected during the fitting process. These bins may contain outlier data or sparsely populated regions, and thus contribute relatively little to the likelihood or error minimization criteria used during model fitting. However, they still influence the cumulative structure of the distribution and are fully accounted for by the CvM metric. As such, the CvM statistic may reveal shape mismatches that are not evident from visual inspection or metrics focused solely on central regions.

3. Results

We first aimed to test whether the weighted skew-normal distributions presented in Section 2.2 can accurately model both one-peak and two-peak cases, thereby supporting cancer diagnosis and the monitoring of therapeutic treatments. To this end, AFM elasticity spectra from murine breast tumors were analyzed to evaluate changes in tumor nanomechanics during tranilast treatment. The weighted skew-normal distribution was then applied to model these data from our previous

14 days: Dataset 2

Fig. 4. Representative experimental data and fitted curves (Dataset 2), 14 days after cancer cell implantation. (a) Control sample and (b) tranilast-treated sample. (c) Comparison of the two fitted curves. There is no clear evidence of a two-peak pattern in either the control group or the tranilast effect. In both cases, the R^2 coefficient and CvM metric approached 1 and 0, respectively, indicating a highly accurate fit. The cumulative probability functions, shown in (d) and (e) for the control and tranilast-treated samples, further confirm the quality of the fitting.

study [33] as input. In cancer tissues, the Young's modulus distribution exhibits a characteristic two-peak structure, reflecting the contribution of soft cancer cells and stiffer ECM components, such as overexpressed collagen. Since tranilast reduces collagen levels, the two peaks are expected to converge, reflecting a reduction of the stiffer HEP toward the softer LEP. This study tests whether the proposed model can capture this behavior quantitatively. In each case (i.e., 14, 21, and 28 days after cell transplantation), two representative datasets (Dataset 1 and Dataset 2) from different biopsies, are presented. Dataset 1 and Dataset 2 correspond to AFM measurements obtained from tissue biopsies from different animals. Specifically, Dataset 1 includes measurements from two mice (one control and one Tranilast-treated), whereas Dataset 2 comprises measurements from a separate experiment on two additional mice (one control and one Tranilast-treated). Therefore, these datasets represent independent biological replicates rather than repeated measurements of the same specimen, providing a more robust assessment of inter-individual variability in tissue mechanical properties.

In Fig. 3, a characteristic dataset of experimental data (Dataset 1) and the corresponding fitted curves, representing 14 days after cancer cell implantation, are presented. Both the control sample (Fig. 3a) and the tranilast-treated sample (Fig. 3b) are shown.

The fitting parameters in each case are clearly presented within each figure. In Fig. 3c, the two fitted curves are compared directly. For the control group, two distinct peaks are observed ($\xi_1 = 0.9393\text{kPa}$, $\xi_2 = 1.8491\text{kPa}$). In contrast, tranilast treatment appears to exert a clear

effect in this case, as evidenced by the emergence of a single-peak distribution ($\xi_1 = 0.8250\text{kPa}$). In both cases, the R^2 coefficient and the CvM metric were close to 1 and 0, respectively, indicating the high accuracy of the fitting. The cumulative probability functions are also shown in Fig. 3d and e for the control and tranilast-treated case, respectively. These graphs demonstrate the accuracy of the fitting process. The data collected at 14 days post cancer cell implantation did not always provide a clear view of the Young's modulus distribution or the effect of tranilast, as illustrated in Fig. 4. This is likely because the tumor had not yet developed large enough or due to heterogeneity among different mouse [33]. However, the weighted skew-normal distribution accurately captured the observed Young's modulus distributions in both control and treated tissues, as confirmed by R^2 and CvM metrics.

The same data processing procedure was also applied to the samples collected 21 days after cancer cell implantation (Figs. 5 and 6). In this case, no evidence of the characteristic two-peak cancer pattern was observed as well. Nevertheless, the fitting remained accurate in all cases.

At 28 days post cancer cell implantation, a distinct two-peak pattern was observed in the control group (Figs. 7 and 8), whereas the tranilast-treated group exhibited a single-peak distribution in the first case (Dataset 1, Fig. 7b, c) and a clear presence of the two peaks in the second case (Dataset 2, Fig. 8b,c).

The comparative graphs in Figs. 7c and 8c clearly demonstrate the change in mechanical distribution induced by tranilast. In this case, the time interval after cancer cell implantation was sufficient, and the

21 days: Dataset 1

Fig. 5. Representative experimental data and model fits from mice (Dataset 1), 21 days after cancer cell implantation, for the control group (**Figure a**) and the tranilast-treated group (**Figure b**). The fitted curves are also shown comparatively in **Figure c**. No distinct two-peak pattern was detected in either group, although the weighted skew-normal distribution still provided highly accurate fits, as confirmed by the cumulative probability functions (**Figure d** for the control group and **Figure e** for the tranilast-treated group).

duration of tranilast treatment was also adequate. Beyond evaluating the fitting curves in **Figs. 7a,b** and **8a,b**, tranilast treatment caused the ξ parameters to converge in both cases. As a result, the right-hand peak progressively approached the left-hand peak. This provides a quantitative assessment of tranilast's effects on cancer tissue and offers a mathematical framework to track the drug's effects, thereby improving treatment monitoring.

4. Discussion

The objective of this work was to provide a mathematically rigorous description of the Young's modulus distributions of cancerous tissues, including untreated (control) and tranilast-treated samples. We sought to determine whether a weighted skew-normal distribution could effectively model both cases, thereby enhancing cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring. The study examined the sensitivity of AFM elasticity spectra to evaluate changes in murine tumor nanomechanics during treatment with tranilast, a drug known to reduce collagen levels in solid tumor models. In cancer tissues, the Young's modulus distribution typically exhibits a two-peak structure, reflecting the contributions of soft cancer cells and stiffer components such as collagen, part of the desmoplasia (which is a cancer specific fibrosis). We hypothesized that tranilast treatment would progressively shift the higher elasticity peak (HEP) toward the lower elasticity peak (LEP), potentially merging

into a single peak at low modulus values. Accordingly, the aim of this paper was to mathematically characterize Young's modulus distributions using appropriate functions. This approach is motivated by the widespread observation of two-peak elastic property distributions in various cancer types. In particular, the pioneering study by Plodinec et al. [26] revealed distinct nanomechanical characteristics among normal, benign, and malignant breast tissues. By analyzing AFM data, the authors separated cellular and matrix contributions, based on the assumption that tumor progression is associated with simultaneous extracellular matrix stiffening and cancer cell softening. Consequently, malignant breast tissue displayed a broad elastic modulus distribution with two clearly distinguishable maxima, LEP and HEP, while normal and benign tissues exhibited relatively uniform stiffness. Similar bimodal stiffness distributions have also been reported in human liver tissue and other cancer types, including esophageal, renal, colon, and papillary carcinomas [3]. In **Fig. 9**, we present the evolution of the distributions for Dataset 1 (**Fig. 9(a)**) and Dataset 2 (**Fig. 9(b)**) of the control groups (i.e., without Tranilast treatment) at 14, 21, and 28 days post-implantation of cancer cells, showing the transition from a one-peak to a two-peak distribution.

The proposed mathematical model successfully captured this behavior. The fitting accuracy of the model was quantitatively assessed using the typical R-squared coefficient and the Cramér-von Mises (CvM) criterion. The CvM metric is particularly suitable for this application as

21 days: Dataset 2

Fig. 6. Representative experimental data and model fits from mice, 21 days after cancer cell implantation (Dataset 2), are shown for the control group (**Figure a**) and the tranilast-treated group (**Figure b**). A direct comparison of the fitted curves is presented in **Figure c**. In both groups, no distinct two-peak pattern was observed, yet the weighted skew-normal distribution achieved highly accurate fits, as further supported by the cumulative probability functions (**Figure d** for the control group and **Figure e** for the tranilast-treated group).

it captures differences in the overall shape of cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) by measuring the integrated squared difference between the empirical and fitted CDFs. A small CvM value (close to zero) and a high R^2 value (close to one) indicate a strong agreement between the fitted distribution and the experimental data. In all cases, the high accuracy of the fit was confirmed by these metrics. The analysis of biopsies collected at different time points after cancer cell implantation provided key insights. At 14 and 21 days post-implantation, no distinct two-peak pattern was consistently observed in either group, presumably because the tumor had not yet fully developed. However, at 28 days post-implantation, a distinct two-peak pattern was clearly observed in the control group, while the tranilast-treated group exhibited a single-peak distribution in the first case (Dataset 1) and a convergence of the two peaks in the second case (Dataset 2). This confirmed that the time interval and treatment duration were sufficient to induce the characteristic changes in mechanical distribution. The convergence of the ξ parameters in the treated group provides a quantitative assessment of tranilast's effects on cancer tissue, offering a mathematical means to track the drug's influence and enhance treatment prognosis.

By applying our novel modeling approach to established datasets, we ensured that the observed effects of tranilast treatment could be quantitatively evaluated in a robust and reproducible manner, thereby strengthening the validity and generalizability of our conclusions.

It is also important to note that the selection of an appropriate model

for fitting the experimental data was non-trivial. In AFM elasticity maps of cancerous tissues, the distributions of Young's modulus are typically asymmetric, heterogeneous, and often multimodal, reflecting the coexistence of mechanically distinct regions, such as soft cancerous cells and stiffer collagen fibrils within the extracellular matrix. Moreover, although the measured modulus values span a wide range (up to approximately 10 kPa), a strong concentration of measurements is observed at low values, around 1 kPa. When classic distributions such as the weighted lognormal, Weibull, or gamma distributions are employed, the models are forced to rise extremely steeply to capture the first peak while simultaneously attempting to represent the second peak and the long tail, a limitation arising from the fact that these distributions are defined only for positive x-axis values. As a result, the fit is suboptimal, either because the position of the first peak does not align with the experimental data or because information associated with the second peak and the tail is lost. In contrast, the weighted skew-normal distribution offers greater flexibility, as it is defined for negative x-axis values, allowing the distribution to stretch smoothly over the data without requiring an abrupt rise. Although no negative values are present in the histogram, only the positive x-axis portion of the skew-normal fit was retained in practice. This approach enables a smooth representation of both peaks while preserving the tail, thereby providing an improved description of the mechanical heterogeneity of biological tissues.

In addition, an important observation to be discussed concerns the

28 days: Dataset 1

Fig. 7. Experimental data and fitted curves from a representative dataset (Dataset 1), corresponding to 28 days after cancer cell implantation. **Panels (a) and (b)** show the control and tranilast-treated samples, respectively, while **(c)** presents a direct comparison of the fitted curves. The control group exhibits two distinct peaks, whereas tranilast treatment results in a single-peak distribution, highlighting the effect of the treatment. In both cases, the R^2 coefficient and CvM metric approached 1 and 0, respectively, indicating high fitting accuracy. The differences in **Figure d** are mainly due to low-probability bins ('small bins'), which have little effect on the identification of the two-peak structure. To reduce their influence, cumulative probability graphs were normalized using a 5% threshold, excluding bins with an area smaller than 5% of the maximum value, thereby emphasizing the dominant peaks (in this case the 'small' bins are on the right part of the histogram). **(e)** The weighted skew-normal distribution provided perfect fit for the tranilast-treated group.

opposite patterns observed in Datasets 1 and 2 for the 14-day treatment condition (Figs. 3 and 4). Specifically, in Dataset 1, a two-peak distribution is observed for the control sample, whereas the tranilast-treated sample exhibits a single peak, as expected. Conversely, in Dataset 2, the opposite behavior is seen, which may initially appear unexpected. This pattern can be explained by the early stage of tumor development: at day 14, the tumor had not fully developed in all cases, and tranilast

treatment, initiated on day 14, had not yet exerted a measurable mechanical effect in every sample. As a result, a single-peak Young's modulus distribution may be observed in control samples due to the underdeveloped tumor microenvironment.

In contrast, the appearance of a two-peak distribution in treated samples at this early time point likely reflects emerging mechanical heterogeneity, where collagen-rich extracellular matrix components

28 days: Dataset 2

Fig. 8. Experimental data and fitted curves from another representative dataset (Dataset 2), 28 days after cancer cell implantation. **Panels (a) and (b)** show the control and tranilast-treated samples, respectively, while **(c)** presents a direct comparison of the fitted curves. The control group displays two distinct peaks, whereas tranilast treatment causes the right-hand peak to progressively approach the left-hand peak, highlighting the treatment effect. In both cases, the R^2 coefficient and CvM metric approached 1 and 0, respectively, indicating high fitting accuracy. Differences in **panel (d)** are primarily due to low-probability (“small”) bins, which have minimal impact on the identification of the two-peak structure. To reduce their influence, the cumulative probability graphs were normalized using a 5% threshold, excluding bins with an area smaller than 5% of the maximum value, thereby emphasizing the dominant peaks (here, the smaller bins are located at the center of the histogram). **(e)** The weighted skew-normal distribution provided perfect fit for the tranilast-treated group.

remain present and mechanically distinguishable. The limited duration of drug exposure is not expected to significantly suppress collagen-related stiffening, allowing two mechanically distinct contributions to coexist. Therefore, depending on the region tested, a one-peak distribution may be observed in the control sample, while a two-peak

distribution may appear in the treated sample, explaining the opposite trends observed in Datasets 1 and 2. This behavior is consistent with empirical observations of tumor mechanics and delayed pharmacological effects reported in [33]. Importantly, despite this early-stage variability, the weighted skew-normal distribution consistently provides an

Fig. 9. Evolution of the distributions for Dataset 1 (**Figure (a)**) and Dataset 2 (**Figure (b)**) of the control groups (i.e., without Tranilast treatment) at 14, 21, and 28 days post-implantation of cancer cells, illustrating the transition from a one-peak to a two-peak distribution.

accurate and robust description of all datasets across time points and treatment conditions, fulfilling the primary objective of this study.

Another important point to discuss concerns the choice of 10 bins for histogram construction. This selection was guided by considerations of statistical robustness and the intrinsic characteristics of AFM-derived Young's modulus datasets obtained from biological tissues. In such measurements, excessive binning can lead to sparsely populated bins, artificial peak splitting, and increased sensitivity to measurement noise, potentially distorting the underlying mechanical information. It should also be emphasized that the appearance of two peaks in cancer tissue histograms reflects distinct mechanical contributions arising from soft cancer cells and stiffer extracellular matrix components, such as collagen. However, neither contribution is associated with sharply defined or universally accepted reference values for Young's modulus. For example, cancer cell stiffness is generally expected to fall within a broad range of approximately 1–2 kPa within an overall modulus span of about 10 kPa. Under these conditions, the use of very narrow bins is inappropriate, as it may introduce spurious sub-peaks within the same mechanical regime, falsely suggesting additional mechanically distinct populations. Consequently, using a moderate number of bins, such as 10, allows the dominant mechanical features of the tissue to be resolved while avoiding discretization-induced artifacts that could obscure the true biomechanical interpretation of the data. A bin number of 10 thus represents a balanced compromise between resolution and statistical stability, capturing the main features of the probability distribution without introducing bin-related artifacts.

In addition, a binning sensitivity analysis was performed by reconstructing representative histograms using 15 and 20 bins. A characteristic example is presented in Fig. 10, which represents the same data as Fig. 8 but using different numbers of bins. Specifically, the data were represented using 10, 15, and 20 bins. The resulting distributions showed no qualitative changes in peak positions, skewness, or overall shape.

Beyond the present application, this modeling approach offers broad utility. It can be applied to other cancer types or fibrotic tissues where stiffness is heterogeneous, as well as to evaluate responses to different therapeutic interventions. A representative example is lung fibrosis [34]. Moreover, the weighted skew-normal distributions can be extended to cases where Young's modulus distributions exhibit three or more peaks by adding additional terms to Eq. (10). It is important to note that in many biological tissues, multimodal distributions of Young's modulus ($n > 2$) are observed [48]. In such cases, the analysis presented in this paper can be readily extended by adding additional terms to Eq. (10), i.e., in the weighted skew-normal distribution as already mentioned. Although multimodal distributions could be used, a bimodal approach was employed for cancer tissues in this study. Biological

tissues are inherently mechanically heterogeneous, with individual cells, whether normal or cancerous, exhibiting substantial variability in their stiffness. Cancer progression further amplifies this heterogeneity through extracellular matrix stiffening, which could give rise to multimodal Young's modulus distributions. Nevertheless, for AFM-based diagnostics, the most informative features are the two primary elasticity modes: the lower peak, predominantly arising from cells, and the higher peak, corresponding to extracellular matrix components. These two peaks capture the essential differences between normal and malignant tissues and have clear physical interpretations, representing distinct tissue constituents. While a multimodal fit might improve mathematical accuracy, it complicates tissue classification, as the low-elasticity peak may fragment into subpeaks and the high-elasticity peak may reflect the complex composition of the matrix. Focusing on the lower and higher elasticity peaks provides a straightforward and robust approach for distinguishing normal from malignant tissues. However, future extensions could include modeling mixtures with more than two peaks when appropriate [48], spatial mapping of stiffness, dynamic monitoring of temporal changes, and correlations with imaging or molecular markers, thereby enhancing the predictive power and general applicability of the approach.

In addition, future research will focus on extending the present probabilistic framework through direct comparison with machine learning-based approaches, such as machine learning models and algorithms and artificial neural networks. While the current study emphasizes a physically interpretable description of Young's modulus distributions for quantifying tissue mechanical heterogeneity, machine learning techniques may offer complementary advantages in automated classification, particularly in cases where overlapping or closely spaced peaks hinder clear separation. A systematic evaluation of classification accuracy, robustness, and sensitivity to subtle changes in modulus distributions will be undertaken, with special emphasis on assessing how these methods perform relative to the probabilistic model in detecting therapy-induced mechanical alterations. Such a combined analysis is expected to clarify the respective strengths and limitations of physics-informed modeling and data-driven approaches in AFM-based tissue mechanics.

5. Conclusions

This study introduced a quantitative framework for modeling Young's modulus distributions of cancerous tissues using weighted skew-normal distributions. The model effectively captured both single- and two-peak behaviors, reflecting tissue heterogeneity and treatment response. Application to AFM elasticity spectra showed that tranilast treatment led to peak convergence, with accuracy confirmed by R^2 and

10 bins

15 bins

20 bins

Fig. 10. The histograms presented in Fig. 8 were constructed using different numbers of bins. The cases of 10, 15, and 20 bins, along with the corresponding fitted weighted skew-normal distributions, are shown for comparison. Changes in the number of bins neither reduced the accuracy of the fitting process nor altered the presented results.

Cramér–von Mises criteria. Using previously published datasets allowed robust validation without additional experiments. The approach is broadly applicable to other cancers, fibrotic tissues, and therapeutic interventions, and can be extended to multi-peak distributions by adding terms to the model.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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